

A Summary of Laws for Car Window Tint in Three Countries: US, UK and Japan

Kohei Matsumura¹, Ritsumeikan University

In this paper, we summarize car window tint legislation in three countries: US, UK and Japan. The legislation itself is for keeping drivers sight and avoiding car accidents, however, it differs among countries and states. We reviewed provisions of the car window tint legislation and summarized them in the paper. This may help readers' understanding of related laws to develop a novel in-car devices especially the devices attaching on the windows and/or replacing the window with the device.

1. Light Transmission, Reflective and Area

Most of the laws for car window tint use Visible Light Transmission percentage (VLT%) as darkness. It also defines rules for tinting materials, specifically, restrictions of using reflective. For the front windshield, most of the countries restrict applying window tint except certain area of the window. With respect to these three constraints, light transmission, reflectiveness and tint area, this paper summarizes the laws in three country: US, UK and Japan. Table 1. shows laws related to window tint for cars.

2. Front Windshield

Table 2. shows a summary of windows tint for front windshield. There are most strong restrictions for adding window tint to front windshield because of safety. In US, four out of 50 states proscribe adding tint to front windshield. Other 46 states, UK and Japan prohibit to add window tint to most area of front windshield. Only top 4–6 inches or top 20% is allowed to add tint for these states/countries.

3. Front Side Windows

Table 3. shows a summary of windows tint for front side windows. Since glasses for a car itself has 80% VLT average, we assumed that the laws prohibit to add tint if the laws define over 70% VLT. The laws in ten out of 50 states for US, UK and Japan proscribe to tint front side screen. However over 40 states allow window tinting under 50% VLT%.

¹ matsumur@acm.org

4. Back Side Windows

Table 4. shows a summary of windows tint for back side windows. Most of states/countries allow window tinting under 50% VLT%. Only five states restrict window tint for back side windows, however, for SUV and Van, two out of five states allow window tint. This implies most of states/countries believe that tinting to back side windows does not affect car safety.

5. Rear Windshield

Table 5. shows a summary of windows tint for rear windshield. Similar to the case for back side windows, most of states/countries allow window tinting under 50% VLT%. Only five states restrict window tint for rear windshield.

State / Country	Related Law	Reference Number
Alabama	Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C	[1-7]
Alaska	Alaska State Legislature Alaska Statutes Section 28.5.81	[8]
Arizona	Arizona State Legislature Article 28-959.01	[9]
Arkansas	Arkansas Code of 1987 Title 27 Chapter 37 Subchapter 3	[10]
California	California Legislative Information Vehicle Code Division 12 Chapter 4	[11]
Colorado	Colorado Revised Statues Section 42-4-227	[12]
Connecticut	Connecticut General Assembly 14-99g Section	[13]
Delware	State of Delaware Title 21 Section 4313	[14]
District of Columbia (D.C.)	D.C. Code Section 50-2207.02	[15]
Florida	Florida Statutes Section 316.2951~2956	[16]
Gerogia	Understanding Window Tint Laws	[17]
Hawaii	Hawaii Revised Statutes section 291-21.5	[18]
Idaho	Idaho Statutes Title 49 Chapter 9	[19]
Illinois	Illinois Vehicle Code Chapter 12 Article V	[20]
Indiana	Indiana Code Title 9 Article 19 Chapter 19	[21]
Iowa	Iowa Legislature Title VIII Subtitle 2 Chapter 321.444	[22]
Kansas	Kansas Statute Chapter 8 Article 17 Section 49	[23]
Kentucky	Kentucky Revised Statutes Section 189.110	[24]
Louisiana	Louisiana Revised Statutes 32 Section 361.1	[25]
Maine	Maine Statutes Title 29A Section 1916	[26]
Maryland	Maryland Code section 22-406	[27]
Massachusetts	Massachusetts General Laws Chapter 90 Section 9D	[28]
Michigan	Michigan Vehicle Code section 257.709	[29]
Minnesota	Minnesota Statutes 169.71	[30]
Mississippi	Mississippi Code Section 63-7-59	[31]
Missouri	Missouri Revised Statutes Chapter 307.173	[32]
Montana	Montana Laws Title 61 Chapter 9 Part 405	[33]
Nebraska	Nebraska Revised Statutes Chapter 60. Motor Vehicles § 60-6,257	[34]
Nevada	Nevada Revised Statutes 484D.440	[35]
New Hampshire	New Hampshire Laws Title XXI Chapter 266 Section 58-a	[36]
New Jersey	New Jersey Statutes Title 39:3-75	[37]
New Mexico	New Mexico Statutes Section 66-3-86.1	[38]
New York	New York Consolidated Laws Article 9 Section 375. 12-a	[39]
North Carolina	North Caronlia Legislature Statutes Article 3 Section 20-127	[40]
North Dakota	North Dakota Department of Traffic Chapter 39-21	[41]
Ohio	Ohio Revised Code Title 45 Chapter 4513.241	[42]
Oklahoma	Oklahoma Statutes Title 47-12-422	[43]
Oregon	Oregon Vehicle Code section 815.221	[44]
Pennsylvania	Pennsylvania Code Title 75 Section 4524	[45]
Rhode Island	Rhode Island General Laws Chapter 31-23.3	[46]
South Carolina	South Carolina Title 56 Chapter 5 Section 5015	[47]
South Dakota	South Dakota Code of Law Chapter 32-15-2	[48]
Tennessee	Tennessee Code Title 55 Chapter 9 107	[49]
Texas	Texas Administrative Code Title 37 Part 1 Chapter 21.3	[50]
Utah	Utah Code Title 41 Chapter 6a Part 16 Section 1635	[51]
Vermont	Vermont Statutes Title 23 Section 1125	[52]
Virginia	Code of Virginia Title 46.2 Chapter 10 Section 1052	[53]
Washington	Revised Code of Washington Title 46 Chapter 37 Section 430	[54]
West Virginia	West Virginia Code Article 17C Chapter 15 Section 36a	[55]
Wisconsin	Wisconsin Statutes Section 347.43	[56]
Wyoming	Wyoming Statutes Title 31 Chapter 5 Article 9 Division 3	[57]
United Kingdom	United Kingdom The Road Vehicles (Construction & Use) Regulations 1986	[58, 59]
Japan	Road Transport Vehicle Act 29	[60]

Table 1. State/Country and related laws.

State / Country	VLT	Area	Reflectance	Remarks
Alabama	0%	top 6 inches	20%	
Alaska	0%	top 5 inches	0%	
Arizona	0%	above AS-1 Line	0%	
Arkansas	50%	top 5 inches	0%	
California	0%	top 4 inches	0%	
Colorado	70%	top 4 inches	0%	
Connecticut	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Delaware	0%	above AS-1 Line		
District of Columbia (D.C.)	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Florida	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Georgia	100%		0%	
Hawaii	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Idaho	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Illinois	0%	top 6 inches	35%	
Indiana	30%	above AS-1 Line	25%	
Iowa	0%	above AS-1 Line	0%	Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standard 205
Kansas	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Kentucky	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Louisiana	0%	top 5 inches	0%	
Maine	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Maryland	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Massachusetts	0%	top 6 inches		
Michigan	0%	top 4 inches	0%	
Minnesota	100%			
Mississippi	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Missouri	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Montana	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Nebraska	0%	above AS-1 Line	0%	
Nevada	0%	above AS-1 Line		
New Hampshire	35%	above AS-1 Line		
New Jersey	100%			No Tints
New Mexico	0%	above AS-1 Line		
New York	70%	top 6 inches		
North Carolina	0%	above AS-1 Line		
North Dakota	70%		0%	
Ohio	0%	above AS-1 Line	0%	
Oklahoma	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Oregon	50%	top 6 inches	13%	
Pennsylvania	0%			
Rhode Island	70%	top 6 inches		
South Carolina	0%	above AS-1 Line	0%	
South Dakota	35%	top 6 inches	0%	
Tennessee	70%		0%	
Texas	25%	above AS-1 Line	25%	
Utah	70%	top 4 inches	0%	
Vermont	100%			
Virginia	70%	above AS-1 Line	20%	
Washington	0%	top 6 inches	35%	
West Virginia	0%	top 5 inches	20%	
Wisconsin	0%	above AS-1 Line		
Wyoming		top 5 inches	20%	
United Kingdom	75%			
Japan	0%	top 20%		

Table 2. A summary of the window tint laws for front windshield.

State / Country	VLT	Area	Reflectance	Remarks
Alabama	32%		20%	
Alaska	-		-	
Arizona	33%		35%	
Arkansas	25%		25%	
California	88%		0%	
Colorado	27%		0%	
Connecticut	35%		27%	
Delware	70%		0%	
District of Columbia (D.C.)	70%		-	55% VLT for SUV, Van
Florida	28%		25%	
Gerogia	32%		20%	
Hawaii	35%		0%	
Idaho	35%		35%	
Illinois	35%		0%	
Indiana	30%		25%	
Iowa	70%		0%	
Kansas	35%		0%	
Kentucky	35%		25%	
Louisiana	40%		20%	
Maine	35%		0%	
Maryland	35%		0%	
Massachusetts	35%		35%	
Michigan	35%	top 4 inches	35%	
Minnesota	50%		20%	
Mississippi	28%		20%	
Missouri	35%		35%	
Montana	24%		35%	
Nebraska	35%		35%	
Nevada	35%		0%	
New Hampshire	100%		0%	
New Jersey	100%		0%	
New Mexico	20%		0%	
New York	70%		0%	
North Carolina	32%		20%	
North Dakota	50%		0%	
Ohio	50%		0%	
Oklahoma	25%		25%	
Oregon	50%		13%	
Pennsylvania	70%		0%	
Rhode Island	70%		-	
South Carolina	27%		0%	
South Dakota	35%		0%	
Tennessee	25%		0%	
Texas	25%		25%	
Utah	43%		0%	
Vermont	100%		0%	
Virginia	50%		20%	
Washington	24%		35%	
West Virginia	35%		20%	
Wisconsin	50%		-	
Wyoming	28%		20%	
United Kingdom	75%		-	
Japan	70%		-	

Table 3. A summary of the window tint laws for front side windows.

State / Country	VLT	Area	Reflectance	Remarks
Alabama	32%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Alaska	37%			37%
Arizona	0%			35%
Arkansas	25%			0%
California	0%			0%
Colorado	27%			0%
Connecticut	35%			21%
Delware	0%			0%
District of Columbia (D.C.)	50%		-	30% VLT for SUV, Van
Florida	28%			25%
Gerogia	32%			20%
Hawaii	3%			0%
Idaho	35%			20%
Illinois	30%			0%
Indiana	30%			25%
Iowa	0%			0%
Kansas	35%			0%
Kentucky	18%			35%8% VLT for SUV, Van
Louisiana	25%			20%
Maine	35%			0%
Maryland	35%			0%
Massachusetts	35%			35%
Michigan	0%			35%
Minnesota	50%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Mississippi	28%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Missouri	0%			35%
Montana	24%			35%
Nebraska	35%			35%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Nevada	0%		-	
New Hampshire	35%			0%0% VLT for SUV, Van
New Jersey	0%			0%
New Mexico	20%			0%
New York	0%			0%
North Carolina	32%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
North Dakota	50%			0%
Ohio	25%			0%
Oklahoma	25%			25%
Oregon	50%			13%
Pennsylvania	0%		-	
Rhode Island	70%		-	
South Carolina	27%			0%
South Dakota	20%			0%
Tennessee	35%			0%
Texas	0%		-	
Utah	0%			0%
Vermont	0%			0%
Virginia	35%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Washington	24%			35%0% VLT for SUV, Van
West Virginia	35%			20%0% VLT for SUV, Van
Wisconsin	35%		-	
Wyoming	28%			20%
United Kingdom	0%		-	
Japan	0%		-	

Table 4. A summary of the window tint laws for back side windows.

State / Country	VLT	Area	Reflectance R	Remarks
Alabama	32%		-	
Alaska	37%		0%	
Arizona	0%		35%	
Arkansas	10%		0%	
California	0%		0%	
Colorado	27%		0%	
Connecticut	35%		21%	
Delaware	0%		0%	
District of Columbia (D.C.)	50%			30% VLT for SUV, Van
Florida	15%		35%	
Georgia	32%		20%	
Hawaii	35%		0%	
Idaho	35%		35%	
Illinois	30%		0%	
Indiana	30%		25%	
Iowa	0%		0%	
Kansas	35%		0%	
Kentucky	18%		35%	8% VLT for SUV, Van
Louisiana	12%		20%	
Maine	35%		0%	
Maryland	35%		0%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Massachusetts	35%		35%	
Michigan	0%		35%	
Minnesota	50%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Mississippi	28%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Missouri	0%		-	
Montana	24%		35%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Nebraska	35%		35%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Nevada	0%			
New Hampshire	35%		0%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
New Jersey	0%		0%	
New Mexico	20%		0%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
New York	0%		0%	
North Carolina	32%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
North Dakota	50%		0%	
Ohio	0%		0%	
Oklahoma	25%		25%	
Oregon	50%		13%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Pennsylvania	0%			
Rhode Island	70%			0% VLT for SUV, Van
South Carolina	27%		0%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
South Dakota	20%		0%	
Tennessee	35%		0%	
Texas	25%		25%	
Utah	0%		0%	
Vermont	0%		0%	
Virginia	35%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Washington	24%		35%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
West Virginia	35%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
Wisconsin	35%			
Wyoming	28%		20%	0% VLT for SUV, Van
United Kingdom	0%			
Japan	0%			

Table 5. A summary of the window tint laws for rear windshield.

References

1. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-1. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-1.htm>
2. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-2. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-2.htm>
3. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-3. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-3.htm>
4. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-4. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-4.htm>
5. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-5. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-5.htm>
6. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-6. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-6.htm>
7. Alabama State Legislature Section 32-5C-7. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://alisondb.legislature.state.al.us/alison/codeofalabama/1975/32-5C-7.htm>
8. Alaska State Legislature Alaska Statutes Section 28.5.81. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.legis.state.ak.us/basis/statutes.asp#28.05.081>
9. Arizona State Legislature Article 28-959.01. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.azleg.gov/FormatDocument.asp?inDoc=/ars/28/00959-01.htm&Title=28&DocType=ARS>
10. Arkansas Code of 1987 Title 27 Chapter 37 Subchapter 3. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.lexisnexis.com/hottopics/arcodes/Default.asp>
11. California Legislative Information Vehicle Code Division 12 Chapter 4. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://leginfo.ca.gov/faces/codes_displayText.xhtml?lawCode=VEH&division=12.&title=&part=&chapter=4.&article=
12. Code of Virginia Title 46.2 Chapter 10 Section 1052. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://law.lis.virginia.gov/vacode/title46.2/chapter10/section46.2-1052/>
13. Colorado Revised Statutes Section 42-4-227. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <https://legiscan.com/CO/text/HB1251/id/243372/Colorado-2011-HB1251-Amended.pdf>
14. Connecticut General Assembly 14-99g Section. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://search.cga.state.ct.us/r/statute/dtsearch.asp?cmd=getdoc&DocId=11793&Index=I%3A%5Cindex%5Csurs&HitCount=2&hits=647+648+&hc=2&req=%28number+contains+14-99g%29&Item=0>
15. D.C. Code Section 50-2207.02. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.lexisnexis.com/hottopics/dccode/>
16. Florida Statutes Section 316.2951-2956. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from

- http://archive.flsenate.gov/Statutes/Index.cfm?App_mode=Display_Statute&URL=Ch0316%2Ftitl0316.htm&StatuteYear=2005&Title=-%3E2005-%3EChapter+316
17. Glass/Window Tinting. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://drivinglaws.aaa.com/tag/glass-window-tinting/>
 18. Hawaii Revised Statutes section 291-21.5. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://www.capitol.hawaii.gov/hrscurrent/Vol05_Ch0261-0319/HRS0291/HRS_0291-0021_0005.htm
 19. Idaho Statutes Title 49 Chapter 9. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <https://legislature.idaho.gov/statutesrules/idstat/Title49/T49CH9/SECT49-944/>
 20. Illinois Vehicle Code Chapter 12 Article V. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.ilga.gov/legislation/ilcs/ilcs4.asp?DocName=062500050HCh.+12+Art.+V&ActID=1815&ChapterID=49&SeqStart=138700000&SeqEnd=139200000>
 21. Indiana Code Title 9 Article 19 Chapter 19. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://iga.in.gov/legislative/laws/2016/ic/titles/009/>
 22. Iowa Legislature Title VIII Subtitle 2 Chapter 321.444. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <https://www.legis.iowa.gov/publications/search/document?fq=id:819089&pdid=803705&q=321.438#321.444>
 23. Kansas Statute Chapter 8 Article 17 Section 49. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://www.kslegislature.org/li/b2017_18/statute/008_000_0000_chapter/008_017_0000_article/008_017_0049a_section/008_017_0049a_k/
 24. Kentucky Revised Statutes Section 189.110. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.lrc.ky.gov/Statutes/statute.aspx?id=6309>
 25. Louisiana Revised Statutes 32 Section 361.1. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://legis.la.gov/Legis/Law.aspx?d=88294>
 26. Maine Statutes Title 29A Section 1916. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.mainelegislature.org/legis/statutes/29-A/title29-Asec1916.html>
 27. Maryland Code section 22-406. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.lexisnexis.com/hottopics/mdcode/>
 28. Massachusetts General Laws Chapter 90 Section 9D. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <https://malegislature.gov/Laws/GeneralLaws/PartI/TitleXIV/Chapter90/Section9D>
 29. Michigan Vehicle Code section 257.709. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from [http://www.legislature.mi.gov/\(S\(tjbjw10oozcpdmmjs0hkq24\)\)/mileg.aspx?page=getObject&objectName=mcl-257-709](http://www.legislature.mi.gov/(S(tjbjw10oozcpdmmjs0hkq24))/mileg.aspx?page=getObject&objectName=mcl-257-709)
 30. Minnesota Statutes 169.71. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <https://www.revisor.leg.state.mn.us/statutes/?id=169.71>
 31. Mississippi Code Section 63-7-59. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.lexisnexis.com/hottopics/mscode/>
 32. Missouri Revised Statutes Chapter 307.173. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.moga.mo.gov/mostatutes/stathtml/30700001731.html>
 33. Montana Laws Title 61 Chapter 9 Part 405. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://leg.mt.gov/bills/mca/title_0610/chapter_0090/part_0040/section_0050/0610-0090-0040-0050.html
 34. Nevada Revised Statutes 484D.440. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.leg.state.nv.us/Nrs/NRS->

- [484D.html#NRS484DSec430](#)
35. New Hampshire Laws Title XXI Chapter 266 Section 58-a. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.gencourt.state.nh.us/rsa/html/XXI/266/266-58-a.htm>
 36. New Jersey Statutes Title 39:3-75. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://lis.njleg.state.nj.us/cgi-bin/om_isapi.dll?clientID=565716524&Depth=4&TD=WRAP&advquery=windshield&headingswithhits=on&infobase=statutes.nfo&rank=&record=%7BF14A%7D&softpage=Doc_Frame_Pg42&wordsaroundhits=2&x=0&y=0&zz=
 37. New Mexico Statutes Section 66-3-86.1. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://public.nmcompcomm.us/nmpublic/gateway.dll/?f=templates&fn=default.htm>
 38. New York Consolidated Laws Article 9 Section 375. 12-a. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://public.leginfo.state.ny.us/lawssrch.cgi?NVLWO>
 39. North Carolina Legislature Statutes Article 3 Section 20-127. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from http://www.ncleg.net/EnactedLegislation/Statutes/PDF/BySection/Chapter_20/GS_20-127.pdf
 40. North Dakota Department of Traffic Chapter 39-21. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.dot.nd.gov/manuals/mv/MVD38.pdf>
 41. Ohio Revised Code Title 45 Chapter 4513.241. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://codes.ohio.gov/orc/4513.241>
 42. Oklahoma Statutes Title 47-12-422. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://law.justia.com/codes/oklahoma/2016/title-47/section-47-12-422/>
 43. Oregon Vehicle Code section 815.221. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.oregon.gov/ODOT/DMV/docs/vcb/VCB815.pdf>
 44. Pennsylvania Code Title 75 Section 4524. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.legis.state.pa.us/WU01/LI/LI/CT/HTM/75/00.045.024.000..HTM>
 45. Revised Code of Washington Title 46 Chapter 37 Section 430. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://apps.leg.wa.gov/RCW/default.aspx?cite=46.37.430>
 46. Rhode Island General Laws Chapter 31-23.3. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://webserver.rilin.state.ri.us/Statutes/TITLE31/31-23.3/31-23.3-4.HTM>
 47. South Carolina Title 56 Chapter 5 Section 5015. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://www.scstatehouse.gov/code/t56c005.php>
 48. South Dakota Code of Law Chapter 32-15-2. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://sdlegislature.gov/statutes/DisplayStatute.aspx?Type=Statute&Statute=32-15>
 49. State of Delaware Title 21 Section 4313. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://delcode.delaware.gov/title21/c043/sc01/index.shtml>
 50. Tennessee Code Title 55 Chapter 9 107. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from <http://law.justia.com/codes/tennessee/2010/title-55/chapter-9/part-1/55-9-107/>
 51. Texas Administrative Code Title 37 Part 1 Chapter 21.3. Retrieved April 10, 2017, from

